

**Impact of career plateau and supervisory support on career satisfaction: A study in offshore
outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka**

Wickramasinghe, V.

Jayaweera, M

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V., & Jayaweera, M. (2010). Impact of career plateau and supervisory support on career satisfaction: A study in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka. Career Development International, 15(6), 544-561.

This Version is available at: doi: 10.1108/13620431011084402

Purpose- To examine the effect of career plateau (hierarchical plateau and job content plateau) and supervisory career support on career satisfaction.

Design/methodology/approach- A random sample of 119 IT professionals full-time employed in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka responded. Multiple regression was used for the data analysis.

Findings- Supervisory career support significantly predicts career satisfaction. However, hierarchical plateau and job content plateau do not significantly predict career satisfaction.

Originality/value- Although IT employees attached to the offshore IT firms may be identified as a unique population is worthy of empirical investigation, details on how they actually manage their careers remain obscure. The findings of this study provide interesting implications to individuals' career satisfaction and will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Keyword(s): career plateau; career satisfaction; hierarchical plateau; job content plateau; supervisor support.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Globalisation, new technologies, and the emergence of new occupations make changes to the employment landscape and have important implications for career management (Ruigrok *et al.*, 1999; Baruch, 2003). The offshoring of services (such as packaged software, information technology [IT] services, banking and insurance) to developing countries is growing at a faster rate and estimated that more than 18 million jobs were likely to go offshore by 2008 (World Bank, 2006, p.8-12). Although it is estimated that more than 150 countries are competing to offer offshored services to a handful of wealthy countries, some of the most attractive offshoring countries are China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Philippines, Thailand, and Sri Lanka (World Bank, 2006, p.11).

The current study is confined to explore career satisfaction of IT professionals engaged in the offshore IT firms in Sri Lanka. An IT professional is defined as a person engaged in producing IT related output as his or her primary job function (SLICTA, 2007, p.7). This definition does not include the employees engaged in IT enabled services (ITES) as their main job function does not involve producing IT related output, although they use IT in their day-to-day work (SLICTA, 2007, p.7). Some of the broad job categories covered by the definition are database administration and development, business analysts and system integration, system and network administration, programming and software engineering, and solutions and technical architect (SLICTA, 2007, p.7).

In the knowledge intensive offshore business sectors such as IT, economic value is found more in intangibles and less in tangibles. Therefore, knowledge and expertise IT professionals possess is perceived as vital to the success in the knowledge based economy (Powell and Snellman, 2004). Sri Lanka's offshore outsourcing sector emerged in the mid 1990s and currently has approximately a 30,000 member IT workforce of which 45% have a Bachelor's degree or a higher qualification in IT (SLICTA, 2007). In this regard, the World Bank (2006) states that although cost is an important factor in attracting offshore

businesses, it is not the only criterion that clients consider in making site selection. In terms of labour quality and external labour market size, the World Bank (2006, p.29) states “despite its small (labour force) size, the country (Sri Lanka) turns out a significant number of technically qualified individuals especially in IT, accounting and business management”. Hence, the World Bank (2006, p. 20-29) suggests that Sri Lanka’s comparative advantage is in the quality and not in the quantity of its labour force.

Understanding career issues of IT professionals in this sector is important for several reasons. First, relatively little empirical research has investigated career issues of IT professionals (without confining to offshore context) outside the Western world (e.g. Appelbaum *et al.*, 2002; Counsell, 1999; Ituma and Simpson, 2006; Lee, 2002). Second, it is very rare to find empirical evidence on the work environment and work practices in the global offshore IT sector as most all empirical studies examine employees attached to the ITES sector (e.g. Bhatnagar, 2007; Budhwar *et al.*, 2006a, 2006b; Raman *et al.*, 2007; the special issues of *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 12 No. 4 in 2003, and *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 12 No. 4 in 2002).

Third, previous studies conducted in Sri Lanka provide evidence that IT firms tend to acquire individuals with required capabilities from the external labour market (Mahahettige, 2008), and the premium on the industry experience is very high in compensation decisions (Mahahettige, 2008, Sanjeevani, 2009). Further, opportunities available for promotion are few and far between as there are typically two layers in the organisational hierarchy- top management and technical specialists (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Furthermore, training and development activities provided by the firms emphasize short-term productivity (Mahahettige, 2008). In this regard, one could argue that IT professionals today have a much shorter cycle before their skills become obsolete (Edvinsson and Camp, 2005; Lee, 2002). However, the evidence from the Sri Lankan context reveals that employers expect new recruits to stay with them for about two years from the day they start (SLICTA, 2007).

This implies that employers do not expect long-term employee commitment from their IT professionals.

It is possible to argue that the offshore outsourced IT firms' preferred people management practices have been tailored to meet business objectives conditioned by the global competitive environment. The issues of addressing economic growth and industrialisation has influenced the Sri Lankan government to initiate mechanisms to attract foreign investment and modern technology. This has resulted in extensive opportunities for IT firms and for IT personnel. However, foreign clients of offshore IT firms could make this sector a "foot loose" or highly mobile business sector. As a consequence, on the one hand, IT firms choose to employ personnel in the most efficient manner (Mahahettige, 2008, Sanjeevani, 2009; Wahundeniya, 2009). The firms hire employees from the external labour market, focus on their short-term job performance with short-term productivity targets, and pay them market-based rewards maintaining internal equity (Mahahettige, 2008). Further, IT firms are likely to standardize jobs to facilitate rapid replacement, considering employees as "short-timers" (Mahahettige, 2008). On the other hand, the employers' preference for job specific skills and experience creates an environment for IT professionals to hop from one workplace to another and maximize their employability (Mahahettige, 2008; Wickramasinghe, 2009). This may give them a feeling that their experience is rewarded (Mahahettige, 2008). This leads to high labour turnover of IT employees (Wickramasinghe, 2009). In the above context, it is possible to assume that the career issues faced by IT professionals in the offshore outsourced IT firms could be different from other traditional business sectors. Therefore, one could argue that the offshore IT employees are a unique population that is worthy of empirical investigation.

The objective of this research, therefore, is to explore the extent to which career plateaus (hierarchical plateau and job content plateau) and supervisory career support influence career satisfaction. Hierarchical plateau and job content plateau are identified as variables that explain the nature of careers in the offshore outsourced IT sector. Supervisory

career support is identified as a factor that affects employees' career development. By so doing, the study examines the role of career plateau (hierarchical plateau and job content plateau) and supervisory career support in explaining IT professionals' career satisfaction. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide insight into individual career satisfaction and provide useful information to better understand suitable career management practices to be adopted in the offshore IT firms. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

In order to provide context for this article, in the next section, the relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Career satisfaction as a measure of career success

The widely-accepted conceptualisation of an individual's career is the lifelong sequence of role-related experiences of an individual (Hall, 1990, 2002). The literature differentiates between an individual's objective (external) and subjective (internal) feelings towards his or her career, and accordingly, objective and subjective measures of career success (Arthur *et al.*, 2005; Melamed, 1996; Poole *et al.*, 1993; Hall and Moss, 1998). An individual's objective feeling towards his or her career is identified as a sequence of official positions, salary changes, formal structures and titles, all of which are publicly accessible and defined external to the person (Melamed, 1996; Gould and Penley, 1984). In contrast, an individual's subjective feeling towards his or her career is identified as a self-judgement of his or her own success (Poole *et al.*, 1993). An individual's subjective feeling towards his or her career has been measured in terms of various criteria, for example, future prospects (e.g. Ayree *et al.*,

1994), job satisfaction (see Arthur *et al.*, 2005), and career satisfaction (e.g. Barnett and Bradley, 2007; Cox and Harquil, 1991; Ng *et al.*, 2005).

Corresponding to the objective and subjective feelings towards the career of an individual, career success is the positive psychological and work-related outcomes accumulated as a result of his or her work experiences (Seibert and Kraimer, 2001). The research on the objective and subjective career success is diverse. One body of research studies relies on the argument that objective career success affects subjective career success (e.g. Poole *et al.*, 1993). Another group of studies elevates the role of subjective career success over the objective career success (e.g. Aryee *et al.*, 1994). The third group of studies insists that the objective and subjective sides of career success are interdependent (e.g. Seibert *et al.*, 2001). In each body of research, authors have often used cross-sectional designs and relied on what is statistically measurable (Arthur *et al.*, 2005). Previous studies found that individuals with a higher subjective career success feel happier and more successful about their careers relative to their own internal standards (Nabi, 2003; Korman *et al.*, 1981). Therefore, it is important to investigate subjective career success as it has implications for psychological well-being and the quality of work-life (Peluchette, 1993).

Career satisfaction was chosen as a subjective career success measure for this study. Past studies conceptualised the term career satisfaction viewing it as the entirety of work-related experiences over the span of a person's life (e.g. Gattiker and Larwood, 1986; Judge *et al.*, 1995; Lounsbury *et al.*, 2008). For instance, some studies identified career satisfaction as the extent to which an individual believes his or her career progress is consistent with his or her own goals, values and preferences (e.g. Barnett and Bradley, 2007; Erdogan *et al.*, 2004; Heslin, 2003; Seibert and Kraimer, 2001). Some other studies identified career satisfaction as an individual's feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with his or her entire career (e.g. Lounsbury *et al.*, 2008). Further, career satisfaction is also referred to an individual's perception of his or her up-to-date career accomplishments and

prospects for future advancement (e.g. Gattiker and Larwood, 1986; Judge *et al.*, 1995; Nauta *et al.*, 2009).

Several past studies suggest that career satisfaction is related to important work outcomes, such as absenteeism (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002) and turnover intention (e.g. Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009; Nauta *et al.*, 2009). For instance, career satisfaction is found to be significantly negatively related to turnover intention (e.g. Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009; Nauta *et al.*, 2009). Previous research investigating the roots of career satisfaction found it to be a product of a variety of job experiences, including hours worked (Wallace, 2001), salary progression (Seibert *et al.*, 1999), career plateau and supervisory career support (e.g. Allen *et al.* 2004; Greenhaus *et al.*, 1990; Kim and McLean, 2008; Lee, 2002; Yarnall, 1998). The current study examines the effect of career plateau and supervisory career support on career satisfaction of offshore IT professionals.

Career plateau

When the career of an individual is seen as a movement within an organisation in terms of both hierarchical and task-oriented movements, career plateau is the lack of such a movement (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). It is valid to express hierarchical career plateau as the point at which future career mobility is in reasonable doubt because the length of time in the present position has been unduly prolonged (Allen *et al.*, 1998; Veiga, 1981). In the common pyramid-shaped organisation virtually everyone's career at one time or another reaches a point where further hierarchical advancement is unlikely as a minority has the opportunity to make it to the top (see, Appelbaum and Santiago, 1997; Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Prager, 1998). However, when firms rely on offshore outsourced work, further advancement within the organisation becomes more unlikely (Wickramasinghe, 2009), and employees have to face the fact that they have to stay in the same position longer than expected (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002).

The literature defines two measures of hierarchical plateau as objective measurement and subjective measurement (Gould and Penley, 1984; Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Slocum *et al.*, 1985; Veiga, 1981). The objective measurement of hierarchical plateau relies on the length of an employee's tenure in the current job (Slocum *et al.*, 1985). Although job tenure does not directly assess whether an individual has reached a plateau, it appears reasonable to assume that a long time in one position indicates limited prospects for upward mobility (McCleese and Eby, 2006). Hence, the objective aspect of career plateau is determined by past decisions (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). The subjective measurement of hierarchical career plateau, in contrast, relies on the self-assessment of chances for promotion and is driven by future expectations at work (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Jung and Tak, 2008). It is suggested that these two dimensions of hierarchical career plateau are independent of each other (Chao, 1990; Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Tremblay and Roger, 1993). Some researchers compared the objective measurement with the subjective measurement and found that self-assessment of promotion chances explained more variance in work attitudes and behaviours than did the objective measurement of job tenure or position immobility (e.g. Chay *et al.*, 1995). However, both subjective and objective dimensions of the concept of hierarchical career plateau stem from the common structure of organisations, i.e., the pyramid (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002).

The absence of new, challenging and varied tasks without possibilities of improvement or learning is called job content plateau (Allen *et al.*, 1998; Bardwick, 1983). This occurs when employees are no longer challenged by their work (Allen *et al.*, 1998). Although it is said that hierarchical plateau may result in job content plateau it is not a necessary consequence (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). As a distinct form of career plateau, job content plateau has received little empirical attention (e.g. Appelbaum and Santiago, 1997; Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009; Bardwick, 1983; Chao, 1990; McCleese and Eby, 2006). Therefore, in the offshore outsourced IT business environment, understanding job content plateauing seems particularly important.

Previous research has examined the relationship between career plateau and employee career satisfaction (e.g. Allen *et al.*, 1998; Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009; Nicholson, 1993). For instance, Allen *et al.* (1998) found evidence for the job content plateau to be more associated with negative work attitudes than the hierarchical plateau. Further, Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel (2009) and Nicholson (1993) did not find a statistically significant relationship between hierarchical plateau and career satisfaction. However, Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel (2009) and Nicholson (1993) found statistically significant negative relationship between job content plateau and career satisfaction. This implies greater importance of meaningful and interesting job assignments for an individual than hierarchical mobility (e.g. Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009). In this regard, Allen *et al.* (1998) argue that employees may recognise hierarchical plateauing as an inevitable part of their organisational life, and promotion may not play an important role in deciding how satisfied employees are with their career. Although empirical studies on career plateauing in the offshore IT outsourcing context is scarce, following Allen *et al.*'s (1998) contention it could be assumed that the hierarchical plateau would not be related to the career satisfaction. This is because individuals already employed in the offshore outsourced IT firms and potential and job seeking individuals to be employed in this particular sector may be well aware of the industry context (Mahahettige, 2008, Sanjeewani, 2009; Wahundeniya, 2009; Wickramasinghe, 2009). Therefore, it is proposed for the study that:

Hypothesis 1: Hierarchical career plateau will not be related to career satisfaction.

With regard to the job content plateauing, the literature reviewed above provides evidence that the job content plateauing is significantly negatively related to the career satisfaction (e.g. Allen *et al.*, 1998; Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009). When considering the offshore IT workers' situation, the findings of past studies provide evidence that the job content would serve as a substitute for the hierarchical career progress (Wahundeniya, 2009). If hierarchical plateauing does not influence IT employees' career satisfaction (as

suggested in H1), the job content plateauing would significantly negatively related to the career satisfaction. Therefore, it is proposed:

Hypothesis 2: Job content plateau will have a significant negative effect on career satisfaction.

Supervisory career support

The literature identifies supervisory career support as a key factor affecting employees' career development (Maurer and Tarulli, 1994; Yarnall, 1998). Employees' careers are likely to be enriched by supportive relationships with their supervisors (Greenhaus *et al.*, 1990; Igbaria and Wormley, 1992; Renwick and MacNeil, 2002). Although the literature advocates the changing nature of careers and shifts the responsibility for control more towards the individual (Arthur *et al.*, 2005; Hall, 1996), it is also viewed as unlikely that individual employees, however committed, can successfully manage their careers without any support from their supervisors (Yarnall, 1998). Supervisory support may take the form of career enhancing functions such as providing challenging assignments, visibility, and sponsorship, as well as psychosocial functions such as counselling, acceptance, and friendship (Greenhaus *et al.*, 1990; Igbaria and Wormley, 1992).

There is some evidence to suggest that the level of discussion an employee has with his or her supervisor on personal development and how positive the relationship are is related to career satisfaction (e.g. Colarelli and Bishop, 1990; Yarnall, 1998). For instance, Yarnall (1998) found a strong correlation between management support and career satisfaction of employees. In addition, some other studies investigated the link between mentoring and career satisfaction (e.g. Allen *et al.* 2004; Aryee and Chay, 1994; Yarnall, 1998), and provide evidence that plateaued employees show a higher level of commitment and satisfaction with the organisation when they have more discussions with their supervisor about their career (e.g. Yarnall, 1998). Additionally, the literature provides evidence that

supervisory career support positively relates to an individual's performance or effectiveness (e.g. Colarelli and Bishop, 1990; Yarnall, 1998). In the context of the information systems literature, too, the importance of supervisory career support has been consistently emphasised as a determinant of an individuals' performance in work assignments (e.g. Couger, 1988; Igbaria and Wormley, 1992; Greenhaus *et al.*, 1990). However, the impact of supervisory career support on career satisfaction of IT employees' has been subjected to limited research. Based on the above reviewed literature that indicates supervisory career support may positively influence career satisfaction, it is proposed:

Hypothesis 3: Supervisory career support will have a significant positive effect on career satisfaction.

The framework developed for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample

The study was carried out using a survey-based approach. For the study an IT professional is defined as a person with/or equal to degree-level qualification, who is primarily engaged in the creation and provision of IT related output as his or her primary job function as a fulltime employee in the offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka. A random sample of IT employees was selected from the list of 36 firms that were registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI). Board of Investment of Sri Lanka is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output. A contact person was identified at each firm. This person was asked to randomly identify IT

professionals and distribute the link to the on-line survey questionnaire via e-mail (also refer to the section on *methods of data collection*). Of the 300 self-administered questionnaires distributed in the fourth quarter of 2008, a total of 119 usable responses resulted in 40% response rate. The demographics of the sample are shown in Table I. Information regarding population characteristics of IT professionals in the offshore outsourced IT firms are difficult to be found in Sri Lanka. However, the demographics of the sample of our study do not show a deviation from the details of the sample characteristics depicted in prior independent studies of Wickramasinghe (2009) and SLICTA (2007), where both studies collected data in 2006.

Take in Table I

Measures

For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: Eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.*, 2006).

Career satisfaction. Career satisfaction was measured by the five-item scale from Greenhaus *et al.* (1990). This scale has been used in prior research by Igbaria (1991), Igbaria and Wormley (1992), and Lee (2002) in the context of IT personnel. Responses were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.768, Eigenvalue=2.29, and explained variation=71.62%.

Supervisory career support. Supervisory career support was measured by the nine-item scale from Greenhaus *et al.* (1990), which has been used in prior research by Igbaria and Wormley (1992) in the context of IT personnel. Responses were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.812, Eigenvalue=3.98, and explained variation=77.82%.

Job content plateau. Job content plateau was measured using the six-item scale from McCleese and Eby (2006), which elicits employees' perceptions of the probability of future challenges and responsibilities in their jobs and has been used in previous research on job content plateauing (e.g. Allen *et al.*, 1998). The higher scores on this measure indicate greater perceptions of being job content plateaued. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha =.712, Eigenvalue =2.59, and explained variation = 72.95%.

Hierarchical plateau. Hierarchical plateau was operationalised as the length of an employee's tenure in the current job. The previous empirical studies classified respondents into plateaued and not-plateaued based on the firm tenure (e.g. Veiga, 1981, Gould and Penley, 1984). For instance, Veiga (1981) and Gould and Penley (1984) classified employees as hierarchical plateaued if tenure in their current position was seven years or more. Our extensive review of literature in the popular databases (such as of Business Source Premier, ABI/Inform, Emerald, ScienceDirect, and Wiley Blackwell) failed to find recent empirical studies that investigated hierarchical plateau either to provide backing for the operationalisation of the prior studies mentioned above or to identify new methods of operationalisation. Further, as the respondents of our study completed the on-line questionnaire anonymously, we are unable to gather data to assess the appropriate cut-off points from each respondent's organisation. Therefore, following the prior studies (e.g.

Veiga, 1981, Gould and Penley, 1984) we considered IT professionals to be in a hierarchical career plateau if they had been in their current job for seven years or more. Of the 119 respondents, 64% were identified as not-plateaued (coded 0), and 36% were identified as plateaued (coded 1).

Control variables. One firm characteristic and three individual demographic characteristics were controlled. Firm size was assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the number of full-time employees in the organisation. Age was measured in years. Gender (females=0, males=1) and marital status (single=0, married=1) were taken as dichotomous variables.

Methods of data collection

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. The self-administered survey questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample that fit with the intended sample of the study prior to distribution. Considering the target audience of the study and their capabilities, an on-line questionnaire was developed and the link to the on-line survey distributed via e-mail (also refer to the section on *sample*). When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector, 1994). However, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of the cross-sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs, which can be useful for deriving hypotheses about how people react to jobs. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff

et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003).

Results

Descriptive statistics for the variables of job content plateau, supervisory career support and career satisfaction are shown in Table II.

Take in Table II

Table III shows zero-order correlations between the variables. The correlation between job content plateau and career satisfaction is negative and not significant. Similarly, the correlation between hierarchical plateau and career satisfaction is negative and not significant. The correlation between hierarchical plateau and job content plateau is positive and significant. The correlation between supervisory career support and career satisfaction is positive and significant.

Take in Table III

To determine how the independent variables predict career satisfaction, multiple regression was performed. Results are summarised in Table IV. The model explained 51% of the variance in the career satisfaction (Adj. $R^2=0.508$, $p<0.001$). As expected, H1 is supported. It

is expected in H2 that job content plateau will have a significant negative effect on career satisfaction. However, the results of the analysis do not support H2. Supervisory career support ($\beta=0.658, p<0.001$) has a significant positive effect on career satisfaction, supporting H3. The results also suggest that marital status has a significant positive effect on career satisfaction ($\beta=0.224, p<0.05$), where married workers are more satisfied with their career than single workers.

Take in Table IV

Discussion and concluding remarks

The purpose of the current study was to enhance the understanding of career satisfaction of IT professionals in the context of offshore outsourced IT firms and to examine its association with career plateau and supervisory career support. First, the low mean values obtained for job content plateau suggest that IT professionals are not experiencing job content plateau. The results of the regression analysis showed a negative, but non-significant, relationship between job content plateau and career satisfaction. In this regard, previous studies (e.g. Sanjeevani, 2009; Wahundeniya, 2009) conducted in the context of offshore IT firms provide evidence that firms use several practices to avoid job content plateauing. For instance, firms widely use lateral and cross-functional teams in structuring work (e.g. Sanjeevani, 2009; Wahundeniya, 2009). These lateral and cross-functional moves would be helpful in preventing job content plateauing. Further, the offshore IT firms generate revenue by performing projects for foreign clients, and the work is organised around projects (Sanjeevani, 2009). This project based IT work environment could also facilitate meeting the organisation's needs for flexibility and employees' need for broad-based career experiences.

Second, the study inquired into the objective measurement of hierarchical plateau in terms of the length of an employee's tenure in the current job. The results of the regression analysis suggest that the hierarchical career plateau does not make a significant contribution to the career satisfaction. This finding supports the findings of Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel (2009) and Nicholson (1993). The sample of our study was highly educated with qualifications in the job related fields. Although the relevance of educational qualifications to the job is related to career success, they are working in an environment where very little hierarchal movement is available. As suggested by previous researchers (e.g. Allen *et al.*, 1998), IT professionals may have recognised that the hierarchical plateauing is an inevitable part of the organisational life in the offshore IT industry.

Third, when both job content plateau and hierarchical plateau are considered, past research provides evidence that hierarchical plateau has very few effects on career outcomes than job content plateau (e.g. Allen *et al.*, 1998; Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009; Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). However, the findings of the current study suggest that both hierarchical plateau and job content plateau do not have a significant effect on the career satisfaction of individuals. With regard to the relationship between hierarchical plateau and job content plateau, it was found that the correlation between hierarchical plateau and job content plateau is positive and significant. This supports the claim that hierarchical plateau may result in job content plateau although it is not a necessary consequence (see Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002).

Fourth, it was found that supervisory career support significantly predicts career satisfaction. The contemporary literature on career management suggests that the notion of career management has moved beyond organisations to focus on flexible and individual models (e.g. Hall, 2004). Further, it is suggested that organisations and employees have to acknowledge and act upon the increased importance for employees to self-manage their careers (see Strickland, 1997). Yet, the findings of this study suggest that IT professionals need supervisory support for their career satisfaction. This supports the suggestion made by

Yarnall (1998) that line managers could be identified as the first port of call in dealing with career development matters. Hence, one of the implications of the findings is that firms should ensure that line managers have the necessary skills to coach and counsel employees as appropriate.

Fifth, overseas clients of the offshore outsourced IT firms are in a continuous search for locations that give them the best deal (World Bank, 2006), and offshore IT firms' preferred people management practices may be conditioned by the global competitive environment. The reaction of the IT firms to increasing economic pressures may be replacing the traditional long-term, paternalistic career model with a new, short-term, transactional deal, which does not allow much interference from the side of the firms in managing careers of their employees (Mahahettige, 2008, Sanjeevani, 2009). This supports the arguments made by Applebaum and Santiago (1997). As a consequence, IT professionals expect continuous support from the part of the immediate supervisor for their career satisfaction.

Overall, from a theoretical viewpoint, this study makes a contribution to the analysis of career issues of IT professionals in offshore outsourced IT firms. As very little work has been directed towards their career satisfaction, the findings of the study open the door for future investigations. Therefore, it could be expected that the findings of this study would lead to the advancement of this area as a field of inquiry. Further, the findings could be used to assist in both organizations and individuals to apply strategic decisions in managing individual careers.

Limitations of the study and future research

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing quantitative methodology with a sample confined to full-time IT professionals employed in offshore IT firms. For the study purposes, hierarchical career plateau was operationalised based on the objective measurement of years of tenure in the present job. Although this measure was widely used

in the previous research, future studies could collect data on the subjective measures of hierarchical career plateau to complement the objective measure. Further, the study was confined to investigate the influence of career plateau and supervisory support on career satisfaction. However, the findings suggest married employees are more satisfied with their career than those who are unmarried. In addition, findings also suggest a negative relationship between age and supervisory career support suggesting younger workers are more satisfied with supervisory career support than older workers. Therefore, future studies could investigate effects of individual demographic characteristics on career satisfaction. Finally, qualitative and longitudinal studies are needed to enhance the understanding of how IT workers and their employers effectively manage careers.

References

Allen, T.D., Eby, L.T., Poteet, M.L., Lentz, E. and Lima, L. (2004), "Career benefits associated with mentoring for proteges: a meta-analysis", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 89, pp. 127-135.

Allen, T.D., Poteet, M. L. and Russell, J.E.A. (1998), "Attitudes of managers who are more or less career plateaued", *The Career Development Quarterly*, Vol. 47, pp. 159-172.

Appelbaum, S.H. and Santiago, V. (1997), "Career development in the plateaued organization", *Career Development International*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 11-20.

Appelbaum, S.H., Ayre, H. and Shapiro, B.T. (2002), "Career management in information technology: a case study", *Career Development International*, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 142-158.

Armstrong-Stassen, M. and Ursel, N.D. (2009), "Perceived organizational support, career satisfaction, and the retention of older workers", *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 82, pp. 201–220.

Arthur, M.B., Khapova, S.N. and Wilderom, C.P.M. (2005), "Career success in a boundaryless career world", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp. 177-202.

Aryee, S. and Chay, Y.W. (1994), "An examination of the impact of career-oriented mentoring on work commitment attitudes and career satisfaction among professional and managerial employees", *British Journal of Management*, Vol. 5, pp. 241-249.

Ayree, S., Chay, Y.W. and Tan, H.H. (1994), "An examination of the antecedents of subjective career success among a managerial sample in Singapore", *Human Relations*, Vol. 47 No. 5, pp. 487-509.

Bardwick, J.M. (1983), "SMR forum: plateauing and productivity", *Sloan Management Review*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 67-73.

Barnett, B.R. and Bradley, L. (2007), "The impact of organizational support for career development on career satisfaction", *Career Development International*, Vol. 12 No. 7, pp. 617-636.

Baruch, Y. (2003), "Career systems in transition: a normative model for career practices", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 32 No. 2, pp. 231-251.

Bhatnagar, J. (2007), "Talent management strategy of employee engagement in Indian ITES employees: key to retention", *Employee Relations*, Vol. 29 No. 6, pp. 640-663.

Budhwar, P.S., Luthar, H.K. and Bhatnagar, J. (2006a), "The dynamics of HRM systems in Indian BPO firms", *Journal of Labour Research*, Vol. 27 No. 3, pp. 339-360.

Budhwar, P.S., Varma, A., Singh, V. and Dhar, R. (2006b), "HRM systems of Indian call centres: an exploratory study", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 17 No. 5, pp. 881-897.

Chao, G.T. (1990), "Exploration of the conceptualization and measurement of career plateau: a comparative analysis", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 181-193.

Chay, Y.W., Aryee, S. and Chew, I. (1995), "Career plateauing: reactions and moderators among managerial and professional employees", *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 6 No. 1, pp. 61-78.

- Colarelli, S. and Bishop, R. (1990), "Career commitment: function, correlates and management", *Group and Organisational Studies*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 158-176.
- Couger, J.D. (1988), "Motivators vs. demotivators in the IS environment," *Journal of Systems Management*, Vol. 39 No. 6, pp. 36-41.
- Counsell, D. (1999), "Careers in Ethiopia: an exploration of careerists' perceptions and strategies", *Career Development International*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 46-52.
- Cox, T. and Harquil, C. (1991), "Career paths and career success in early career stages of male and female MBAs", *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, Vol. 39 No. 1, pp. 54-75.
- Edvinsson, L. and Camp, J. (2005), "Intelligent remuneration in the knowledge economy for growth of intellectual capital", *Journal of Human Resource Costing and Accounting*, Vol. 9, pp. 112-122.
- Erdogan, B., Kraimer, M.L. and Liden, R.C. (2004), "Work value congruence and intrinsic career success: the compensatory roles of leader-member exchange and perceived organizational support", *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 57 No. 2, pp. 305-332.
- Gattiker, U.E. and Larwood, L. (1986), "Subjective career success: a study of managers and support personnel", *Journal of Business and Psychology*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 78-94.
- Gould, S. and Penley L.E. (1984), "Career strategy and salary progression: a study of their relationship in a municipal bureaucracy", *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, Vol. 34, pp. 244-265.
- Greenhaus, J.H., Parasuraman, S. and Wormley, W.M. (1990), "Effects of race on organizational experiences, job performance evaluations, and career outcomes", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 33 No. 1, pp. 64-86.
- Hair, J.F.Jr, Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E. and Tatham, R.L. (2006), *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 6th Ed. India: Pearson Education.
- Hall, D.T. (1990), *Careers in Organizations*. Santa Monica, CA: Goodyear

Hall, D.T. (1996), "Protean careers of the 21st century", *Academy of Management Executive* Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 8–16.

Hall, D.T. (2002), *Careers In and Out of Organisations*, Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.

Hall, D.T. (2004), "The protean career: a quarter century journey", *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, Vol. 65 No. 1, pp. 1-13.

Hall, D.T. and Moss, J.E. (1998), "The new protean career contract", *Organizational Dynamics*, Winter, pp. 22–38.

Heslin, P.A. (2003), "Self- and other-referent criteria of career success", *Journal of Career Assessment*, Vol. 11 No. 3, pp. 262-286.

Igbaria, M. (1991), "Job performance of MIS professionals: an examination of the antecedents and consequences", *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, Vol. 8 No. 2, pp. 141-171.

Igbaria, M. and Wormley, W.M. (1992), "Organizational experiences and career success of MIS professionals and managers: an examination of race differences", *MIS Quarterly*, December, pp. 507- 529.

Ituma, A. and Simpson, R. (2006), "The chameleon career: an exploratory study of the work biography of information technology workers in Nigeria", *Career Development International*, Vol. 11 No. 1, pp. 48-65.

Judge, T.A., Cable, D. M., Boudreau, J.W. and Bretz, R.D.Jr, (1995), "An empirical investigation of the predictors of executive career success", *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 48, pp. 485-519.

Jung, J-H. and Tak, J. (2008), "The effects of perceived career plateau on employees' attitudes- moderating effects of career motivation and perceived supervisor support with Korean employees", *Journal of Career Development*, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 187-201.

Kim, N. and McLean, G.N. (2008), "Stability and dominance in career success orientation in South Korean employees", *Human Resource Development International*, Vol. 11 No. 1, pp. 19–34.

Korman, A.K., Wittig-Berman, U. and Lang, D. (1981), "Career success and personal failure: alienation in professionals and managers", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 342-360.

Lee, P.C.B. (2002), "Career goals and career management strategy among information technology professionals", *Career Development International*, Vol. 7 No. 1 pp. 6-13.

Lounsbury, J.W., Steel, R.P., Gibson, L.W. and Drost, A.W. (2008), "Personality traits and career satisfaction of human resource professionals", *Human Resource Development International*, Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 351–366.

Mahahettige, D.P. (2008), *Measurement and reporting of Human capital in IT organisations in Sri Lanka*, unpublished MBA dissertation, Department of Management of Technology, Univeristy of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Maurer, T.J. and Tarulli, B.A. (1994), "Investigation of perceived environment, perceived outcome and person variables in relationship to voluntary development activity by employees", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 79 No. 1, pp. 3-14.

McCleese, C.S. and Eby, L.T. (2006), "Reactions to job content plateaus: examining role ambiguity and hierarchical plateaus as moderators", *The Career Development Quarterly*, Vol. 55, pp. 64-76.

Melamed, T. (1996), "Career success: an assessment of a gender specific model", *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 69 No. 3, pp. 217-242.

Nabi, G.R. (2003), "Situational characteristics and subjective career success: the mediating role of career-enhancing strategies", *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. 4 No.6, pp. 653-672.

Nachbagauer, A.G.M. and Riedl, G. (2002), "Effects of concepts of career plateaus on performance, work satisfaction and commitment", *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. 23 No. 8, pp. 716-733.

Nauta, A., van Vianen, A., van der Heijden, B., van Dam, K. and Willemssen, M. (2009), "Understanding the factors that promote Employability orientation: the impact of

employability culture, career satisfaction, and role breadth self-efficacy”, *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 82, pp. 233-251.

Ng, T.W.H., Eby, L.T., Sorensen, K.L. and Feldman, D.C. (2005), “Predictors of objective and subjective career success: a meta-analysis”, *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 58, pp. 367-408.

Nicholson, N. (1993), “Purgatory or place of safety? The managerial plateau and organizational age grading”, *Human Relations*, Vol. 46, pp. 1369–1389.

Peluchette, J. (1993), "Subjective career success: the influence of individual difference, family, and organizational variables", *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 43, pp. 198-208.

Podsakoff, P., MacKenzie, S., Lee, J-Y. and Podsakoff, N., (2003), “Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies”, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 88 No. 5, pp. 879-903.

Poole, M.E., Langan-Fox, J. and Omodei, M. (1993), “Contrasting subjective and objective criteria as determinants of perceived career success: a longitudinal study”, *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 66, pp. 39–54.

Powell, W.W. and Snellman, K. (2004), "The knowledge economy", *Annual Review of Sociology*, Vol. 30, pp. 199-220.

Prager, K.P. (1998), "Assessing career goals and skills", *Information Systems Management*, Vol. 17, pp.73-77.

Raman, R.S., Budhwar, P. and Balasubramanian, G. (2007), “People management issues in Indian KPOs”, *Employee Relations*, Vol. 29 No. 6, pp. 696-710.

Renwick, D. and MacNeil, C.M. (2002), “Line manager involvement in careers”, *Career Development International*, Vol. 7 No. 7, pp. 407-414

Ruigrok, W., Pettigrew, A.W., Peck, S. and Whittington, R. (1999), "Corporate restructuring and new forms of organising: evidence from Europe", *Management International Review*, Vol. 2, pp. 41-64.

Sanjeevani, K.L.S. (2009), *Human resource management practices in software development organisations in Sri Lanka*, unpublished MBA dissertation, Department of Management of Technology, Univeristy of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Seibert, S.E. and Kraimer, M.L. (2001), "The five-factor model of personality and career success", *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 58, pp. 1-21.

Seibert, S.E., Crant, J.M. and Kraimer, M.L. (1999), "Proactive personality and career success", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 84, pp. 416-427.

Seibert, S.E., Kraimer, M.L. And Liden, R.C. (2001), "social capital theory of career success", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 44, pp. 219–237.

SLICTA. (2007). *Rising demand: the increasing demand for IT workers spells a challenging opportunity for the IT industry-National IT workforce survey*, Sri Lanka ICT Association, Colombo.

Slocum, J.W., Cron, W.L., Hansen, R.W. and Rawlings, S. (1985), "Business strategy and the management of plateaued employees", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 28 No. 1, pp.133-154.

Spector, P.E. (1994), "Using self-report questionnaires in OB research: a comment on the use of a controversial method", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 15, pp. 385-392.

Strickland, R. (1997), "Self-development in a business organization", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 11, pp. 30-39.

Tremblay, M. and Roger, A. (1993), "Individual, familial and organizational determinants of career plateau", *Group and Organization Management*, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 411-435.

Veiga, J.F. (1981), "Plateaued versus nonplateaued managers: career patterns, attitudes, and path potential", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 566-578.

Wahundeniya, W.M.I.K.B. (2009), *Analysis of the effects of organizational structure on software development companies in Sri Lanka*, unpublished MBA dissertation, Department of Management of Technology, Univeristy of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka

Wallace, J.E. (2001), "The benefits of mentoring for female lawyers", *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 58 No. 3, pp. 366–391.

Wickramasinghe, V. (2009), "Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 413-431.

World Bank (2006), *Offshore to Sri Lanka: finding Sri Lanka's offshoring niche*, World Bank South Asia Finance and Private Sector Development Unit, World Bank (Colombo Office), Sri Lanka.

Yarnall, J. (1998), "Line managers as career developers: rhetoric or reality?" *Personnel Review*, Vol. 27 No. 5, pp. 378-395.

Figure

Figure 1: Research model

Tables

Table I: Sample description

Sex:	
Male	63%
Female	37%
Marital status:	
Single	43%
Married	57%
The highest level of qualification:	
Professional qualifications [†]	6%
Bachelor's degree	67%
Postgraduate degree [‡]	27%
Age:	
Mean	31 years
Median	31 years
S.D.	2.48
Minimum	23 years
Maximum	38 years
Tenure in the present firm:	
Mean	4.17
Median	4.0
S.D.	2.98
Minimum	9 months
Maximum	11 years

Note: N=119

S.D.= standard deviation

[†] Membership in British Computer Society, Australian Computer Society, and Project Management Professional.

[‡] M.Sc. in information Technology, M.Sc. in Computer Science, and Master of Business Administration (MBA) specialised in Information Technology, MBA specialised in Management of Technology, and MBA (general).

Table II: Descriptive analysis

	Mean	S.D.
<i>Job content plateau:</i>		
I do not expect to be constantly challenged in my job in the future	2.92	1.14
My current job tasks and activities will not become routine for me in the future	2.92	0.76
I will not continue to learn and grow in my current job	2.81	1.31
My current job responsibilities will not increase significantly in the future	2.76	0.78
I will not be challenged in my current job	2.54	0.87
My current job will not continually require me to develop my abilities and knowledge	2.48	0.99
<i>Supervisory career support:</i>		
My supervisor takes the time to learn about my career goals and aspirations.	3.82	0.68
My supervisor cares about whether or not I achieve my career goals	3.95	0.76
My supervisor keeps me informed about different career opportunities for me in the organization	3.62	1.06
My supervisor makes sure I get the credit when I accomplish something substantial on the job	3.87	0.61
My supervisor gives me helpful feedback about my performance	4.17	0.67
My supervisor gives me helpful advice about improving my performance when I need it	4.10	0.49
My supervisor supports my attempts to acquire additional training or education to further my career	3.93	0.84
My supervisor provides assignments that give me the opportunity to develop and strengthen new skills	3.68	0.81
My supervisor assigns me special projects that increase my visibility in the organization	3.53	0.82
<i>Career satisfaction:</i>		
I am satisfied with the success I have achieved in my career	3.90	0.57
I am satisfied with the progress I have made toward meeting my overall career goals	3.72	0.74
I am satisfied with the progress I have made toward meeting my goals for income	3.82	0.78
I am satisfied with the progress I have made toward meeting my goals for advancement	3.75	0.63
I am satisfied with the progress I have made toward meeting my goals for the development of new skills	3.52	0.75

Table III: Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Gender ^a	.64	.476	1						
2. Marital status ^a	.55	.491	.530**	1					
3. Age	31.36	2.48	.341**	.354**	1				
4. No. of employees ^b	6.49	.49	-.285**	-.278**	-.097	1			
5. Hierarchical plateau ^a	.66	.44	.249**	.352**	.556**	-.067	1		
6. Job content plateau	2.76	.46	-.065	-.060	-.158*	-.024	.135*	1	
7. Supervisory career support	3.85	.46	.009	.090	-.047	-.304**	.426**	.109	1
8. Career satisfaction	3.74	.45	.039	.191*	-.039	-.144	-.125	-.129	.685**

Note: ** significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables.

^b Log transformed.

Table IV: Regression results for career satisfaction

	β
Gender	.060
Marital status	.224*
Age	-.066
No. of employees	-.095
Hierarchical plateau	-.038
Job content plateau	-.087
Supervisory career support	.658***
Model R ² (Adj.)	.508***

Note: * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$.